

“INCORPORATING DIGITAL TOOLS TO UPGRADE SPEAKING SKILLS OF ESP LEARNERS”

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Abstract. *With the development of educational technology, utilizing digital tools into English classes in English for Specific Purposes (ESP) context is playing significant role for both professors and learners. One of the very important productive skills in communication, which is speaking skills, being so crucial in academic and professional development need various enhancing strategies. This research work targets the role of digital tools in improving the speaking skills of ESP learners in different fields like engineering. This paper reviews very technologies, discusses strategic framework for integration, and tests both learners' washback and measurable results. According to the findings of this work, using digital tools into classroom can significantly help to improve fluency, pronunciation, learner autonomy and self-confidence. This work explores how these tools can be involved to improve the speaking abilities of ESP learners, as well as linguistic evolvement with direct professional and academic goals.*

Key words: *development, digital tools, context, ESP, learners, speaking skills, listening skills, applications, website, platforms, technology, pronunciation, language, classroom, integration, computers, strategies, Zo-talk.*

Annotatsiya. *Ta'lim texnologiyalarining rivojlanishi bilan bir qatorda, nofilolog talabalarning o'zlarining maxsus maqsadlarda ingliz tili darslarini raqamli vositalardan foydalangan holda o'rganish professorlar va talabalar uchun muhim rol o'ynaydi. Muloqot qilishdagi eng muhim ko'nikmalardan biri bu gapirish maxorati, va uni rivojlantirish uchun, ya'ni uning nutq qobiliyatlarini, akademik va kasbiy rivojlanishda juda muhim bo'lgan turli xil takomillashtirish strategiyalarini mavjud. Ushbu tadqiqot ishi muhandislik kabi turli nofilolog sohalarda, o'quvchilarining nutq ko'nikmalarini oshirishda raqamli vositalarning roli ularning foydali tomonlari va samaradorligi kabi fikr va mulohazalarga qaratilgan. Ushbu maqolada juda ko'p texnologiyalar ko'rib chiqiladi, integratsiyaning strategik asoslari muhokama qilinadi. Ushbu ish natijalariga ko'ra, ingliz tili darslarida raqamli vositalardan foydalanish ravonlik, talaffuz, o'quvchilarning mustaqilligi va o'ziga ishonchni yaxshilashga yordam beradi. Ushbu ish nofilolog o'quvchilarining nutq qobiliyatini yaxshilash uchun qanday jalb qilinishi mumkinligini, shuningdek, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri professional va akademik maqsadlar bilan lingvistik rivojlanishni o'rganadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Rivojlanish, raqamli vositalar, kontekst, ESP, o'quvchilar, nutq qobiliyatlari, tinglash qobiliyatlari, ilovalar, veb-saytlar, platformalar, texnologiya, talaffuz, til, sinf, integratsiya, kompyuterlar, strategiyalar, Zo-talk.*

Аннотация. *С развитием образовательных технологий использование цифровых инструментов на занятиях по английскому языку в контексте английского языка для специальных целей (ESP) играет важную роль как для преподавателей, так и для учащихся. Один из очень важных продуктивных навыков общения, а именно навыки говорения, будучи столь важным в академическом и профессиональном развитии, требует различных стратегий улучшения. Эта исследовательская работа направлена на роль цифровых инструментов в улучшении навыков говорения учащихся ESP в различных*

областях, таких как инженерия. В этой статье рассматриваются самые технологии, обсуждаются стратегические рамки для интеграции и проверяются как обратная связь учащихся, так и измеримые результаты. Согласно выводам этой работы, использование цифровых инструментов в классе может значительно помочь улучшить беглость речи, произношение, самостоятельность учащихся и уверенность в себе. В этой работе изучается, как эти инструменты могут быть использованы для улучшения навыков говорения учащихся ESP, а также языкового развития с прямыми профессиональными и академическими целями.

Ключевые слова: Развитие, цифровые инструменты, контекст, ESP, учащиеся, навыки говорения, навыки аудирования, приложения, веб-сайт, платформы, технологии, произношение, язык, класс, интеграция, компьютеры, стратегии, Zo-talk.

In the digitalized era, a verity of digital tools, platforms and applications has appeared to help learn languages. English for Specific Purpose aims at teaching English focusing on specific fields like business, medicine, law or engineering. Speaking is considered as the most difficult among all language skills cause of anxiety, lack of real-life experience and less practice. In current period of time, traditional classroom strategies are falling as leaners are keen on technology rather than paper-based learning. It requires the need of alternative way of teaching and learning with the help of various digital tools. There are so many digital tools to improve speaking skills:

- Speech Recognition Software
- AI- Powered Feedback Systems
- Flipgrid speaking app
- Virtual Reality and Simulations
- Pronunciation and Fluency Apps
- Interactive Platforms and Roleplay Games

These all tools can help learners to improve their speaking skills very quickly by providing real world contexts, authentic materials and reliable feedback to ESP students.

One of the most important pluses of digital tools in ESP speaking classes is the development of fluency and accent which is pronunciation. Besides, there are so many applications to support students to speak fluently like Speakometer, Google Speech to Text and ELSA Speak. These applications can assist to determine phonetic errors, shift stress, rhythm and intonation, and practice directed terminology with correct articulation.

These years, it is very difficult to get good results from students with the help of just papers and notebook, which is traditional way of teaching, as they want to be busy with their gadget even in the classroom. It is impossible for youngsters to imagine their life without their mobile phones, because they want to be aware of updated news going on in the world. Social media like: Instagram, Telegram, Facebook involve young learners a lot. Cause of these, teachers have to think something new to use their gadget in the class to have interesting and productive lessons. Integrating technology into classroom can improve the quality of the education, as it is a new and powerful way to involve students' attention. The students of ESP need more speaking to communicate for their own purposes, so the most important skill they have to acquire first is speaking. For this reason, learners should be engaged in the most effective and easy ways to learn the aspects and features of speaking. Once students utter a word they should know where to stress and how to intonate like native speaker, the best solution and way to make it possible is utilizing different tools. Besides, relying on digital tools in the classroom can promote learner

autonomy by permitting students to get the source and speaking tasks at any time they want and need, set their own pace, practice exercises as often as need. Involving different tools into classroom can motivate and engage learners. Speaking in another language – especially professional purposes can cause anxiety. Here digital tools ensure a safe, judgment -free space to practice and test speaking skills repeatedly. As a result, students relief performance and presentation anxiety, reward experimentation with new words, and prepare more thoroughly for interaction. With the help of strong confidence, students get ready to speak in front of audience. As an example of practical speaking application- Flipgrid which is highly evaluated app which can help teachers and learners to develop speaking together with listening. Because, there are different functions like timing, messaging, video taking, posting different questions for students to respond, updating the responses, reposting, texting, etc. Once the teachers post the questions or prompts, they can send the link to the target learners to submit their responses, they can set the time, or change the topic a bit later, they can be automatically updated once it is finished. So, this app is rather productive and easy to apply for teachers as well.

Utilizing technology in the classroom has different benefits and advantages. It is the best way to let students be dominated in the class, as they know digital tools even better than the teacher does. There used to be a teacher who was in the center of the class, taking more, participating more, and acting more. However, in this modern life, students can show themselves off as a leader leading and motivating each other more. Students can also take various responsibilities like controlling each other, helping with the device that they are using to connect to the internet or to teach the instructions of how to use them, which are very interesting and involving process for them.

The other overmentioned applications listed above are also so reliable to use for different purposes and skills in the classroom to get the students motivation. As the speaking is one of the most problematic skill to improve among students and even sometimes teachers, I with one of my students created a web site which can help to showcase speaking and listening enhancement, which is named Zo -Talk. There teachers can run into different functions which can help to engage their students in several TED talks, podcasts, TEDx and different topics to discuss and even teachers can post different prompts for students to submit video responses. Zo-talk (meaning - the first letters of Zulaykho and Ozodbek” who are authors of the APP) is so helpful for students to be motivated to enhance their speaking and listening together as it involves more interactive tasks within. The following pictures can demonstrate the quick framework and outlook of Zo-Talk App. There dashboard, home page, instructions of how to work in Zo-Talk, and different tasks on speaking and listening.

Welcome to Zo-Talk

Zo-Talk is your ultimate companion for mastering English. Whether you're preparing for exams like IELTS or just want to improve your speaking and listening skills, we've got you covered. Our platform offers interactive tests, interesting videos, and a variety of podcasts.

The image shows a four-step guide for using the Zo-Talk app. Each step includes a small screenshot of the app interface and a brief description of the action:

- Step 1: Choose test type**
Select the type of test, for example we chose a speaking test
- Step 2: Login to the app**
Login to the app, if you teacher write your username and password, if you are a student write 6 digit number that your teacher gave to you
- Step 3: Start the test**
Now click on "Start Test" button to start the speaking test
- Step 4: Upload the video**
As soon as you finish your speaking test, click on the "Upload" button so that our teachers can check and evaluate your test

Meet the Team

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Finally, digital tools are compatible with Learning Management System (LMS) like Google Classroom and Moodle, and this help professors to give speaking tasks meeting with course objectives, track students ongoing learning, provide rapport on performance data. By implementing digital tools into the curriculum, teachers can accommodate that speaking learning process is continuous, measurable and connected with ESP learning outcomes.

Digital tools picture how speaking skills are acquired and taught in ESP context. As technology keeps on developing, it will be a new alternative way for equipping ESP students with the speaking skills they need for their own purposes especially for communication. Integrating digital tools into classroom offers a multifaceted approach to evolve ESP speaking skills. With the combination of accessibility, relevance and adaptability, these tools empower students to be confident speakers in their specific major, besides these tools can serve as powerful communicators of speaking proficiency.

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